

Case Study

CASE DESCRIPTION

TITLE: Pioneers in Industry 5.0, where sustainability and technology meet for a responsible food future.

ACTORS

LOCATION: Spain

LEADER(S): UPV

PARTNER 1: FEDACOVA

PARTNER 2: GOURMET, S.A.

TIME PERIOD OF THE PROJECT: M16

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE CASE: Gourmet, a Spanish family-owned sausage company, stands out for its commitment to sustainability and innovation. Since its beginnings in 1975, it has been able to combine tradition and adaptation to new market demands. Its focus on quality, social responsibility and care for the environment have made it a benchmark in the food sector. In addition, its commitment to technology and collaboration between humans and machines position it as an outstanding example of a company adapted to the principles of Industry 5.0.

5.0 ORGANISATIONAL CHANGES OF AGRI-FOOD PROCESSES

2.1. Short description of initial context and needs of organisational changes

Gourmet's continuous growth since its foundation in 1975 has driven an organizational evolution marked by the adoption of Industry 5.0 principles. The transition to the second generation in 2012 catalyzed the professionalization and digitalization of the company; a shift focused on process optimization through advanced technologies, product customization and the implementation of sustainable practices, thus adapting to a competitive market and the demands of conscious consumers in the era of Industry 5.0.

2.2. Challenges on Resilience of Agri-Food processes

The company faces resilience challenges that require, as such, continuous adaptation. The company must balance tradition and innovation to satisfy an increasingly demanding and sustainability-conscious consumer. In addition, competition in the market is intense, requiring operational efficiency and agile responsiveness to market fluctuations and disruptions, such as the fire that hit its facilities in 2017, undoubtedly the greatest difficulty the company has encountered in its entire history, that ravaged the plant in its entirety. Gourmet resurfaced not only recovering its previous activity but also growing and diversifying its business. The

investment in the reconstruction of the plant, estimated at 16 million euros, speaks clearly of the company's ambition to look to the future.

Supply chain management, from the selection of raw materials to distribution, also presents challenges in terms of traceability, quality and sustainability. To be resilient, Gourmet must strengthen its capacity for anticipation, diversify its offer and sales channels, and consolidate its commitment to social and environmental responsibility.

Some of the actions the company has taken to strengthen its resilience include:

- **Diversification of customers and sales channels:** Reducing dependence on a single customer (Valencian retail distribution chain) and exploring new markets and distribution channels.
- **Investment in R&D and innovation:** Developing new products and adapting existing ones to new market trends and consumer demands.
- **Professionalization of management:** Incorporating external talent and creating new departments in order to improve the company's efficiency and responsiveness.
- **Investing in technology:** Modernizing facilities and adopting new technologies to optimize production processes and reduce environmental impact.
- **Strengthening commitment to sustainability:** Implementing responsible practices throughout the value chain and communicating the company's commitment to sustainability to its stakeholders.

2.3. Challenges on sustainability of Agri-Food processes

Gourmet faces significant challenges in the sustainability of its agri-food processes, marked by the need to balance efficient production with environmental and social responsibility. The company must adapt to growing consumer demands and preferences for sustainable products, which implies reviewing and optimizing its entire value chain, from the selection of raw materials to packaging and distribution.

Waste management, reduction of natural resource consumption and minimization of the carbon footprint are critical aspects. In addition, the company must ensure that its practices are consistent with environmental regulations and the expectations of its stakeholders, while maintaining the quality and safety of its products.

Improving sustainability in its processes includes:

- **Investing in cleaner and more efficient technologies:** Reducing water and energy consumption, and minimizing waste generation and emissions.
- **Commitment to sustainable packaging:** Using recyclable and biodegradable materials, and reducing the use of plastics.
- **Collaboration with local suppliers:** Promoting the development of the local economy and reducing the carbon footprint associated with transportation.
- **Commitment to animal welfare:** Ensuring compliance with the highest welfare standards in animal husbandry and transportation.
- **Sustainability certifications:** Obtaining certifications such as the IFS Food certification and the AENOR Conform Animal Welfare certificate.

2.4. Human-Centred Approach for the Agri-Food processes

The worker/consumer focus of Gourmet's processes is manifested in its commitment to the quality and safety of its products, always seeking a balance between taste and health. In addition, the company takes care of its employees, promoting work-life balance, a safe and healthy work environment, encouraging their career development and including the hiring of underprivileged groups. Gourmet actively promotes diversity, collaborating with suppliers CEE (Special Employment Center), companies that are made up of staff with at least 70% of people with disabilities in a degree equal to or greater than 33%.

With 52% women in its workforce and 3 women in its management team out of a total of 7, it has been recognized with the Distintiu Violeta in 2020 for its commitment to equality.

The company is also concerned about the welfare of nearby communities, collaborating with local suppliers and supporting social initiatives in the region, as well as sports, especially women's sports. It sponsors the Picken Claret basketball club and the women's first team of the Les Abelles rugby club. This global approach ensures that Gourmet's agri-food processes are sustainable not only from an environmental point of view, but also from a social one.

METHOD AND SOLUTIONS

3.1. Method

Gourmet has adopted a global approach that embraces several key principles of Industry 5.0:

- **Sustainability:** The company has integrated sustainability into its core strategy, seeking a balance between economic growth, social welfare and environmental protection. This is reflected in its commitment to environmental impact reduction, animal welfare and collaboration with local suppliers.
- **Worker and consumer-focused:** Gourmet values human talent and promotes a safe and healthy work environment. The company also cares about the well-being of its customers, offering quality products that meet their needs and preferences.

Resilience: Gourmet has shown remarkable resilience in the face of challenges such as the 2017 fire. The company has invested in technology and diversification to strengthen its resilience and ensure continuity of operations.

- **Innovation:** Gourmet has adopted new technologies and processes to improve the efficiency, quality and customization of its products. The company has also expanded its product range to adapt to new market trends.

3.2. Concrete organisational solution implemented

Among the organizational solutions implemented by the company are:

- **Investment in new renewable energy sources:** a commitment to renewable energies, particularly solar energy, with an investment of €236,000 in a photovoltaic park with a combined capacity of 362.10kW. Since it began operating, the company has stopped emitting 285 tons of CO₂ into the atmosphere, which represents an average annual saving of 206 tons.
- **Recycling and valorization of the different wastes generated in the manufacturing process:** hazardous waste, paper and cardboard, mixed waste, SANDACH waste and water treatment sludge. Currently, 92% of the company's waste is being treated.
- **Digitalization of the supply chain:** Gourmet has digitized its supply chain, allowing it to have greater traceability of its products and to optimize inventory management and reduce delivery times.
- **Reduction of food waste:** thanks to precautionary measures such as stock reduction and control. In cases where prevention has not been sufficient and

a surplus has been generated, it is donated to charitable organizations such as the Food Bank.

- **Development of new products:** The company is committed to innovation, developing new products that adapt to market trends and consumer needs. It is worth highlighting the incorporation of the ready-to-eat range, which responds to the growing demand for convenience and healthy products.

- **Packaging modernization:** Gourmet has renewed the packaging of its products, using more sustainable materials and improving the design to make it more attractive to consumers. The plastic film used in the base of the trays is 100% recyclable and contains up to 15% recycled plastic, and the packaging of the pâté range is 100% recyclable, with a paper tray that can be disposed of in the blue container, thus reducing the consumption of plastic film by 70%. Gourmet was, thus, four years ahead of the requirement that 100% of its own-brand plastic packaging be recyclable by 2025.

- **Nutritional improvements:** the company has made significant improvements in its products in order to make them healthier. They have reduced additives, eliminated colorants and starch, and reduced salt in their pâtés. In addition, they have developed low-fat, lactose-free chicken and

turkey sausages, highlighting the turkey variety with only 3% fat and 25% less salt.

3.3. Key Skills And Competences Necessary

The key competencies and skills for Gourmet to consolidate its position as a leader in Industry 5.0, leading the transformation towards a more sustainable, resilient and human-centered agri-food model, include the following:

- **Leadership and vision**
- **Innovation and creativity**
- **Collaboration and communication**
- **Technological expertise**
- **Commitment to sustainability**
- **Social responsibility**
- **Resilience / adaptability**
- **Continuous improvement**
- **Food defense**
- **Customer satisfaction and improved service**

3.4. Result and Feedback

- **Premio Fuente de Oro 2021:** Awarded by ASIVALCO for its contribution to the reduction of emissions in the Fuente del Jarro Industrial Park.
- **Distintiu Violeta 2020:** Recognition for its commitment to equal opportunities between women and men and non-discrimination in the company.
- **Premio Empresa 2019:** Award at the I Gala del Deporte Femenino de Valencia Plaza Deportiva for its support to women's sports.
- **I Premio a la Sostenibilidad y la Transparencia Empresarial 2021:** In the Social Commitment category, awarded by OBSET (Observatory of Sustainability and Transparency) for its resilience after the fire at its plant in 2017 and its commitment to its workers.

- **Several quality certifications** such as ISO 9001, IFS y BRC, **among others**.

All these awards and certifications highlight Gourmet's positive impact and commitment to the environment, society and sports, as well as its resilience in the face of adversity.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Gourmet promotes sustainability, digitalization and talent as a competitive advantage, anticipating market demands. The company seeks to consolidate its leadership, issuing sustainability reports and collaborating in the OBSET Observatory. The company's management is attentive to the impact of inflation and uncertainty on consumer preferences, as well as the complexity of its wide range of products. In addition, it faces challenges such as the perception of ultra-processed foods and the negotiating imbalance with supermarkets, including the rise of private labels. Gourmet, aware of the challenges of the dynamic environment, seeks to maintain its leading position in the sector by continually adapting and proactively addressing emerging risks and opportunities.

REFERENCES

- “Empresas y Empresarios ejemplares en sostenibilidad”. Author: César Camisón Zornoza.
- Interviews with the Manager of Gourmet, S.A, Mr. Jaime Álvarez.